

The Analysis of Indian Councils Act of 1909

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Abstract:

“The Indian Councils Act of 1909” was an important Act of the Government of British India and which was a step towards included the Indian representatives in the government. Then this Act referred also to as “Morley- Minto reforms” also named after the Officials of British “Lord Minto” and “Lord John Morley” and they played an important role in drafting of this Act. Both of them were the Viceroy of India and Secretary of State of India in the British rule in India in the year between 1905-1910. In early 20th century, there were two developments that emerged in “national movement in India. The Indian nationalists became very gradually increasingly vocal also and adopted very strong tone even as demand for representation of the native Indians in the government and that period saw appearance of extremist in the national movement and they aimed undermining the foundations of British rule.

Keywords: Viceroy of India, legislatures, Secretary of State, Indians involvement, Indian nationalists, Sayid Hussain Bilgrami, Krishna G Gupta, Chambers of Commerce,

Introduction:

“The Indian Councils Act” of 1909 was introduced in the British Parliament with some of the reforms in legislative councils in India and also increased Indians involvement in government of the British India. This also was commonly called “Morley-Minto Reforms and this research article discuss about background of this Act, important provisions along with the Analysis of this Act.

Background of this Act:

The Government of British termed prevailed political situations in India as ‘Unrest of the Indian’. Lord Minto who denounced extremists but he felt it was also very imperative and to engage with moderates of India and also provide some of the political concessions that came to be package as this reforms. This reforms were very basis of Indian Councils Act of 1909. This Act was relatively very short documents, which consisted of 8 articles and 2 schedules, and all of them were written in the legal style. The core features of this Act was recognition of principles of the elections members to both central and provincial “legislative councils”. The Articles in this Act, among further things, did following: increased amount of legislative councils in the provinces, created aall executive councils in West-Bengal, Bombay and Madras Provinces, introduced office of Vice-President at the level of both legislatures.

This Act also itself was skeletal and this was operationalized by the setting of rules and also regulations which fleshed out very details that also included and extent of franchises, qualification for member of that councils and strikingly, introduction of the separate electorates for also the Muslims. While the nationalists of India welcomed this Act as this Act seemed and to provide opportunity for the Indian and to join government but they were not very happy with this Act’s rules and regulations and

that spelt out details which especially introduction of the electorates separately on basis of the religion and they also viewed as a divisive. Then other some aspects of this Act to disappointed nationalists was very limited franchises and also unreason qualifications that required and to stand for the elections. Indian nationalists, they are not fully satisfied and continued the battle for the substantive form of the self-government in India after this Act was put in the place.

Causes:

- Though the ‘Queen Victoria’ who promised to treat the Indians evenly and also provide the equal opportunities for Indians but only very few of the Indians who received this opportunity.
- The British officials of India who denied work together with the Indians.
- The INC (Indian National Congress) acknowledged several difficulties which faced by Indians to go into Civil Service. So INC began to the demand for representations for more Indians in Legislature.
- The moderates in the INC set forth definite demands to government of British as Extremism was expand within INC Congress. The British accepted that certain demands so as to placate Moderates and also they were also introduced under these reforms.
- On behalf of the INC “GopalS Krishna Gokhale” visited Morley and he demanded the ‘self government’ in India.
- The some of the groups of Muslims who led by Mr Agha Khan (the Simla Deputation) met Viceroy Minto and also they demanded the separate electorates for Muslims.
- In the year 1906 C.E. general election was conducted won by ‘British Liberal Party’. This also increased chances for the Reforms in India.

They also believed that the increasing native's representation in Legislatures would enhanced their rule in the India.

- Thus Morley and Minto who put forth some of the measures that came to be called as Morley Minto reforms.

Provisions of These Reforms

Some important provisions of this Act are as follows:

- The amount of the members in the Legislatures were also increased.
- The numbers of members in Legislative Council in the Central level were increased (from 16 to 60).
- At Legislative Councils in the Provinces number of the whole members was not in uniform and this varied from the Provinces.
- Most of the members in Legislative Council (Central) were official members.
- Same time In Legislative Council of the Province, non official members who were in majority.
- 8 numbers of the seats were reserved for the Muslims.
- 4 numbers of the seats were reserved for the British Capitalists.
- 2 numbers of the seats were reserved for the landlords.
- 13 numbers of the seats were reserved for general electorates.
- These reforms of 1909 mentions that, for elected members, the indirect elections were carried out.
- Elections in the Local bodies electoral college, elected members who in the turn elected members Legislative Council in the Provincial, who in order elected Legislative Council members in Central level of Legislative Councils and members of powers and functions at center and provinces were also enlarged. They can ask questions, pass resolutions supplementary, vote separate substance of budget.
- Satyendra Prasad Sinha who was an Indian, was also appointed into Executive Council of the Viceroy's for first time and he was appointed as the member.
- Two numbers of the Indians were nominated for Council of the 'Secretary of State' for affairs of the Indian. They were 'Sayid Hussain Bilgrami' and 'Krishna G Gupta'.
- The separate representation was provided also for universities, zamindars, presidency corporations, chambers of commerce.
- Separation of electorate was also given to Muslims community in which members of the Muslim were elected by Muslims.
- Thus representation system communally was legalized under the Reform of Minto - Morley

of 1909. For that reason Minto came to be known as "father of communal electorate".

Analysis of this Act:

The leaders of INC were not also satisfied with these reforms. They also demanded for responsible government while this Reform focused on the increase natives participation in the Legislatures. The important main defect of reform was introduction of the separate electorates to Muslims. This also created break in unity of Hindu Muslim and also paved way for partitions of country. The Muslims were given electorate separately along with great number of the seats were reserved unproportionately to the population of the Muslims. The method of election was also indirect and there were the inequalities in franchise. The British government aimed to divide ranks of the Nationalists and turn the Moderates and also Muslims against nationalism tide.

Conclusion:

This Act of 1909 is known as 'Morley- Minto Reforms'. This was instituted to pacify Moderates (In INC) and introducing electorates separately on basis of the religion. Therefore, Lord Minto came to be known as 'Father of Communal Electorate' in India. This Act introducing the 'communal representation' in the politics in India. This was also intended to stem growing tides of the nationalism in India by dividing people into the communal lines. The culminations of these steps were seen in partition of India along with the religious lines. Some of the effects of discrepancy treatment of various religious groups in India can be seen also to present. This Act did nothing granting self-government in colonial India, which was the demand of INC. This Act did increase the participation of Indians in legislative councils, particularly at provincial levels.

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